

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOCIAL CLASS AND ATTITUDE TOWARD TAX EVASION: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Several studies have examined the relationship between attitude toward tax evasion and social class. However, those studies were limited to a single country. The results have been mixed. In some cases, tax evasion was found to be more acceptable among members of the lower social classes. In other studies, the exact opposite was found. A third group of studies found no significant relationship between social class and the acceptability of tax evasion. A fourth group of studies found that the relationship is curvilinear. The present study uses data from the most recent World Values Survey, which interviewed more than 125,000 people in nearly 80 countries. The survey included a question on attitude toward tax evasion. This study examines this data with the goal of determining if there is a correlation between social class and attitude toward tax evasion.

INTRODUCTION

Many studies have been done on tax evasion over the years (Alm, Martinez-Vazquez and Torgler, 2005; Collymore, 2020a & b; McGee, 2012). Some have been empirical (Collymore, 2020a; Torgler & Valev, 2010; Torgler, 2010, 2012), while others have focused on theory (Bird-Pollan, 2020; McGee, 1994, 2004, 2006, 2012; van Brederode, 2020). A few literature reviews have been published, so there is no need to reinvent the wheel here (Collymore, 2020b; Khlif & Ashek, 2015; McGee, 2012). It is a topic that is inherently interdisciplinary. The public finance literature tends to focus on which kinds of taxes are best in certain situations, and what effect a particular tax has on collections (Buchanan & Musgrave, 2001). The public finance literature almost never asks philosophical questions, like when taxation is justified and when it is not, or what determines whether someone is paying their “fair share,” a term that is conveniently undefinable (McGee, 1999).

The economics literature tends to focus on utilitarian approaches, and often takes a macro approach. Politicians and some scholars talk about using the tax system to entice certain behavior (like tax credits) and punish other behavior (like cigarette and alcohol taxes) (Buchanan, 1967; Buchanan & Musgrave, 2001; Jouvenel, 1952; Musgrave, 1959; Musgrave & Peacock, 1958). Some cross-country comparisons of various tax aspects have also been done (Richardson, 2006, 2008). The accounting literature trends to focus on applications and “how to” topics that practitioners find interesting. The legal literature focuses on tax law and cases, and seldom addresses issues of justifiability, since the underlying premise is that the tax must be justified if some legislature passed it.

Some authors have explored philosophical aspects of taxation and tax evasion (Crowe, 1944; McGee, 1994, 2012; van Brederode, 2020), even going so far as to ask the question of whether taxation can even be justified in some cases (Blum & Kalven, 1953; Nozick, 1974) or in any case (Block, 1989, 1993; Block & Torsell, 2020; Chodorov, 1962).

Several studies have examined the religious literature to learn what certain religions have had to say on the subject of taxation and tax evasion. Crowe (1944) surveyed 500 years of Christian (mostly Catholic) religious literature. Gronbacher (1998), Pennock (1998) and Schansberg (1998) discussed various aspects of the Christian view. Bose (2012) reflected on the Hindu literature. Cohn (1998, 2012) and Tamari (1998) expounded on the Jewish view. Green (2020) examined certain taxes from both the Christian and Jewish perspectives. Smith & Kimball (1998) reviewed the Mormon literature. DeMerville (1998) summarized the literature of the Baha'i religion. Ahmad (1995), Jalili (2012) and Yusuf (1971) discussed Islamic view on tax evasion and arrived at seemingly different conclusions.

The present paper focuses on a single aspect of tax evasion, the relationship between social class and attitude toward the acceptability of tax evasion. Several other studies have examined this issue, but those analyses were usually limited to attitudes in one country. The exception was a study by McGee (2012), which examined the relationship between membership in a social class and attitude toward tax evasion for many countries. The McGee study found several different correlations. One group of countries had a positive correlation, where the acceptability of tax evasion increased as one examined the data from the lower classes to the upper classes. Another correlation existed in a different set of countries where the exact opposite was true. In a third set of countries, the middle classes were either more opposed or less opposed to tax evasion than were the upper and lower classes, which formed a curvilinear relationship. One thing the McGee (2012) study did not show was which of the several correlations was dominant. The present study aims to determine whether a dominant correlation exists, and if so, which correlation it is. The present study also uses more recent data than the data that was used in the McGee (2012) study.

METHODOLOGY

Every five years or so, starting in 1981, the people who publish the World Values Surveys (Haerpfer, 2020) conduct individual face-to-face interviews with a wide range of individuals from different educational, social, and religious backgrounds. The latest, Wave 7, asked hundreds of questions to more than 125,000 individuals in nearly 80 countries. One of those questions asked about the justifiability of tax evasion. The interviewer asked respondents to choose a number from 1 to 10 to indicate whether tax evasion was never justified (1) to always justified (10). Not every question was asked in every country. The tax evasion question was asked in 76 countries.

In this study, we examined the relationship between social class and attitude toward the justifiability of tax evasion. The database divided social classes into five groups. Respondents self-identified as being a member of one of the five groups. The social class question was included in the surveys for 47 countries. The results are presented below.

FINDINGS

The present study found that there was no clearly definable correlation between social class and attitude toward tax evasion in some cases, while in other countries there was either a positive, negative, or curvilinear correlation.

Table 1 shows the mean scores for the 47 countries where data are available. The World Values Survey divided social class into five subcategories. Interviewees self-identified as to which class they belonged. A comparison of the highest and lowest mean scores indicates that there is a significant difference of opinion as to the justifiability of tax evasion in nearly all cases. However,

a comparison of the individual mean scores for each class indicates there is more than one uniform trend. In some cases, justifiability increases as one compares the mean scores from lower to upper classes. In other cases, the trend is just the opposite. In a third group of countries, there is either a curvilinear trend, or no discernible trend. A comparison of the highest mean score for each country to the mean score of the upper class finds that they are the same in 26 cases (55.3%). This relationship might be explained by the fact that the upper classes are assessed taxes at a higher rate than the lower classes, and that they resent being exploited. There may be other explanations as well. We will leave an examination of this question for another time.

Table 1
Relationship between Acceptability of Tax Evasion and Social Class
All Countries
(1 = Never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

Country	1 Upper Class	2 Upper Middle Class	3 Lower Middle Class	4 Working Class	5 Lower Class	H Highest level of acceptance	L Lowest level of acceptance
Andorra	2.23	1.79	1.63	1.61	2.19	2.23	1.61
Argentina	3.00	2.38	1.94	2.28	2.37	3.00	1.94
Australia	2.30	2.12	1.92	2.02	1.90	2.30	1.90
Bangladesh	1.83	1.59	1.72	1.66	1.79	1.83	1.59
Bolivia	1.80	2.04	2.03	2.06	2.08	2.08	1.80
Brazil	3.38	2.88	3.04	2.87	3.00	3.38	2.87
Chile	1.67	4.00	2.40	2.37	3.48	4.00	1.67
China	2.35	1.62	1.58	1.43	1.45	2.35	1.43
Colombia	2.76	1.67	2.16	1.76	2.19	2.76	1.67
Cyprus	2.07	1.75	1.46	1.48	1.64	2.07	1.46
Ecuador	3.25	2.29	2.33	2.08	2.67	3.25	2.08
Ethiopia	1.96	1.68	1.41	1.64	1.56	1.96	1.41
Germany – East & West	1.62	1.52	1.52	1.42	1.50	1.62	1.42
Greece	1.31	1.63	1.67	1.65	1.90	1.90	1.31
Guatemala	3.15	2.65	2.19	N/A	2.27	3.15	2.19
Hong Kong	3.89	2.49	2.19	1.91	1.93	3.89	1.91
Indonesia	3.46	2.47	2.21	2.45	3.13	3.46	2.21
Iran	1.67	2.61	2.24	2.38	2.27	2.61	1.67
Iraq	2.50	2.18	2.87	2.78	2.28	2.87	2.18
Japan	2.00	1.33	1.20	1.25	1.19	2	1.19
Jordan	1.80	1.92	2.10	2.21	2.12	2.21	1.80
Kazakhstan	3.26	2.84	3.09	3.00	2.65	3.26	2.65
Kyrgyzstan	2.12	2.10	2.10	2.40	2.99	2.99	2.10
Lebanon	3.08	2.45	2.51	2.76	2.73	3.08	2.45
Macau	1.80	2.21	2.19	2.75	2.68	2.75	1.80
Malaysia	3.92	3.27	3.43	3.29	4.03	4.03	3.27
Mexico	3.63	3.06	2.89	3.02	2.98	3.63	2.89
Myanmar	1.68	1.64	1.56	1.63	1.82	1.82	1.56
New Zealand	2.17	1.58	1.87	1.85	1.85	2.17	1.58
Nicaragua	3.09	2.67	2.13	2.06	2.22	3.09	2.06
Nigeria	1.62	1.62	1.90	1.68	1.83	1.90	1.62
Pakistan	2.20	2.18	1.96	1.84	2.17	2.20	1.84
Peru	1.21	1.70	1.80	1.97	2.05	2.05	1.21
Philippines	5.56	3.71	4.08	4.53	3.71	5.56	3.71

Puerto Rico	2.11	1.59	1.48	1.42	1.54	2.11	1.42
Romania	2.32	2.34	2.06	2.06	2.41	2.41	2.06
Russian Federation	4.76	3.88	3.67	3.42	3.38	4.76	3.38
Serbia	3.55	3.07	2.92	3.79	2.62	3.79	2.62
South Korea	2.00	2.25	2.23	2.41	2.08	2.41	2
Taiwan ROC	1.84	1.77	1.77	1.65	1.93	1.93	1.65
Tajikistan	2.42	2.34	2.47	2.50	2.25	2.50	2.25
Thailand	1.00	1.54	1.84	1.69	1.80	1.84	1
Tunisia	2.06	1.93	1.90	1.68	2.37	2.37	1.68
Turkey	1.40	1.84	1.64	1.59	1.60	1.84	1.40
United States	3.38	1.87	2.01	2.07	2.70	3.38	1.87
Vietnam	4.00	3.10	2.73	2.77	2.44	4	2.44
Zimbabwe	1.92	1.96	1.74	1.94	1.88	1.96	1.74

Table 2 lists the countries where the trend is for mean scores to increase as one compares mean scores from the lower to upper classes. Asia is well represented, with 6 countries (if one includes Russia), followed by Latin America, with 5 countries. Oceania and Europe are represented by only two countries each.

Table 2
Countries Where Justifiability Increases with Social Class
(1 = Never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

Country	1 Upper Class	2 Upper Middle Class	3 Lower Middle Class	4 Working Class	5 Lower Class	H Highest level of acceptance	L Lowest level of acceptance
Australia	2.30	2.12	1.92	2.02	1.90	2.30	1.90
China	2.35	1.62	1.58	1.43	1.45	2.35	1.43
Ecuador	3.25	2.29	2.33	2.08	2.67	3.25	2.08
Guatemala	3.15	2.65	2.19	N/A	2.27	3.15	2.19
Hong Kong	3.89	2.49	2.19	1.91	1.93	3.89	1.91
Japan	2.00	1.33	1.20	1.25	1.19	2	1.19
Mexico	3.63	3.06	2.89	3.02	2.98	3.63	2.89
New Zealand	2.17	1.58	1.87	1.85	1.85	2.17	1.58
Nicaragua	3.09	2.67	2.13	2.06	2.22	3.09	2.06
Pakistan	2.20	2.18	1.96	1.84	2.17	2.20	1.84
Puerto Rico	2.11	1.59	1.48	1.42	1.54	2.11	1.42
Russian Federation	4.76	3.88	3.67	3.42	3.38	4.76	3.38
Serbia	3.55	3.07	2.92	3.79	2.62	3.79	2.62
Vietnam	4.00	3.10	2.73	2.77	2.44	4	2.44

Table 3 lists the countries where the trend is for mean scores to decrease as one compares mean scores from the lower to upper classes. Asia is represented by 3 countries, Latin America by 2, and Europe and Africa by one each.

Table 3
Countries Where Justifiability Decreases with Social Class
(1 = Never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

Country	1 Upper Class	2 Upper Middle Class	3 Lower Middle Class	4 Working Class	5 Lower Class	H Highest level of acceptance	L Lowest level of acceptance
Bolivia	1.80	2.04	2.03	2.06	2.08	2.08	1.80
Greece	1.31	1.63	1.67	1.65	1.90	1.90	1.31
Jordan	1.80	1.92	2.10	2.21	2.12	2.21	1.80
Kyrgyzstan	2.12	2.10	2.10	2.40	2.99	2.99	2.10
Macau	1.80	2.21	2.19	2.75	2.68	2.75	1.80
Peru	1.21	1.70	1.80	1.97	2.05	2.05	1.21
Thailand	1.00	1.54	1.84	1.69	1.80	1.84	1

Table 4 lists the 26 countries that have either a curvilinear trend or no discernible trend. The curvilinear countries had several different patterns. For example, Andorra, Argentina, Cyprus, Indonesia, Romania, Taiwan, Tunisia and the United States had U-shaped or V-shaped trends. Bangladesh, Brazil, Colombia and Malaysia and W-shaped trends. Ethiopia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Lebanon, the Philippines, Tajikistan and Zimbabwe had N-shaped curves, while Chile and Nigeria and a backward N-shaped curve. Iran had an M-curve. South Korea and Turkey had no discernible trend.

Table 4
Countries with a Curvilinear or No Trend
(1 = Never Justifiable; 10 = Always Justifiable)

Country	1 Upper Class	2 Upper Middle Class	3 Lower Middle Class	4 Working Class	5 Lower Class	H Highest level of acceptance	L Lowest level of acceptance
Andorra	2.23	1.79	1.63	1.61	2.19	2.23	1.61
Argentina	3.00	2.38	1.94	2.28	2.37	3.00	1.94
Bangladesh	1.83	1.59	1.72	1.66	1.79	1.83	1.59
Brazil	3.38	2.88	3.04	2.87	3.00	3.38	2.87
Chile	1.67	4.00	2.40	2.37	3.48	4.00	1.67
Colombia	2.76	1.67	2.16	1.76	2.19	2.76	1.67
Cyprus	2.07	1.75	1.46	1.48	1.64	2.07	1.46
Ethiopia	1.96	1.68	1.41	1.64	1.56	1.96	1.41
Germany – East & West	1.62	1.52	1.52	1.42	1.50	1.62	1.42
Indonesia	3.46	2.47	2.21	2.45	3.13	3.46	2.21
Iran	1.67	2.61	2.24	2.38	2.27	2.61	1.67
Iraq	2.50	2.18	2.87	2.78	2.28	2.87	2.18
Kazakhstan	3.26	2.84	3.09	3.00	2.65	3.26	2.65
Lebanon	3.08	2.45	2.51	2.76	2.73	3.08	2.45
Malaysia	3.92	3.27	3.43	3.29	4.03	4.03	3.27
Myanmar	1.68	1.64	1.56	1.63	1.82	1.82	1.56
Nigeria	1.62	1.62	1.90	1.68	1.83	1.90	1.62
Philippines	5.56	3.71	4.08	4.53	3.71	5.56	3.71
Romania	2.32	2.34	2.06	2.06	2.41	2.41	2.06
South Korea	2.00	2.25	2.23	2.41	2.08	2.41	2
Taiwan ROC	1.84	1.77	1.77	1.65	1.93	1.93	1.65
Tajikistan	2.42	2.34	2.47	2.50	2.25	2.50	2.25
Tunisia	2.06	1.93	1.90	1.68	2.37	2.37	1.68

Turkey	1.40	1.84	1.64	1.59	1.60	1.84	1.40
United States	3.38	1.87	2.01	2.07	2.70	3.38	1.87
Zimbabwe	1.92	1.96	1.74	1.94	1.88	1.96	1.74

Table 5 shows the percentage of countries that fall into each of the three categories. More than half of the countries included in the study have either curvilinear trends or no discernible trend. Justification for tax evasion increases as one compares mean scores from lower to upper classes in 29.8 percent of the cases, which is exactly twice as many countries that have a trend in the opposite direction (14.9%).

Table 5
Summary of Relationships

	#	%
Countries where justification for tax evasion increases from lower to upper classes.	14	29.8
Countries where justification for tax evasion decreases from lower to upper classes.	7	14.9
Countries with a curvilinear trend or no discernible trend.	26	55.3
Totals	47	100.0

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings in the present study replicate the findings of other studies, in that several different correlations were identified, depending on the country, and that in a few cases, there seemed to be no correlation. However, the present study determined what the dominant correlation was, something that no prior study had done. It also replicates the only other study of many countries that has been done (McGee, 2012), using more current data, and going into more depth.

There are several areas that could benefit from further research. Although several correlations between views toward the acceptability of tax evasion and social class have been identified, so far there have been no adequate explanations for why there is a correlation, or why there are several different correlations. It would be interesting to know why some countries have a positive correlation while others have a negative correlation, and why a third group of countries has a curvilinear correlation. One way to uncover this information would be to interview large groups of individuals in the various countries and ask them the reason for their viewpoint. However, such a study would be costly. Perhaps that is why it has not been done. However, a series of smaller studies could accomplish the same goal at much lower cost.

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